

Discordant CD₄ cell count and viral load responses to antiretroviral therapy

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ABSTRACT

Most patients starting highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) show suppression of HIV replication below the level of detection (currently <50 HIV-1 RNA copies/mL in most assays), and experience a gradual rise in CD₄ lymphocyte count, which may continue for several years. The CD₄ count response is generally related to the degree of viral load suppression, and this typical pattern of CD₄ and viral load response is associated with a marked improvement in prognosis. In some patients, however, there is discordance in the response. Either there is suppression of viral load but poor recovery of immune function, characterized by little or no CD₄ cell count increase or, conversely, an improvement in CD₄ cell count with incomplete or delayed viral load suppression. Little is known about the pathogenesis of discordant responses, which seems to depend on the interaction of a multitude of viral, host and treatment-related factors. Available evidence indicates that discordant responses are associated with an intermediate risk of death or clinical progression. At present, recommendations for the clinical management of patients with discordant responses to antiretroviral therapy are largely based on observational, uncontrolled data. The development of standardized and universally accepted definitions of discordant responses is necessary to allow meaningful comparisons between studies to be made, as well as to help in the design of trials of possible therapeutic interventions.

KEYWORDS: antiretroviral therapy, viral load, CD₄ lymphocyte count, treatment outcome, cohort, mortality

Introduction

While decrease in viral load and increase in CD₄ cell typically occur together after starting antiretroviral therapy, this does not always happen. Some people who achieve full suppression of HIV do not show much improvement in their CD₄ cell counts, whilst others experience good CD₄ cell recovery despite continued detectable HIV replication. These so-called “discordant” responses tend to occur more often in highly treatment-experienced patients with drug-resistant HIV.

Studies in industrialized countries have shown that discordant response to therapy occurs in 20 to 40% of treated patients, with isolated immunological response being slightly more common than isolated virological response. A recent study of more than 3000 patients receiving highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) in low-income countries in Africa, Latin America and Asia found that the frequency and risk factors for discordant response were similar to those in more developed countries.

A rising CD₄ count indicates improved immune function even in the absence of full HIV suppression. Thus, people on ‘failing’ treatment that does not suppress viral load below 50 copies/ml still may experience reduced risk of opportunistic infections, improved overall health and prolonged survival. In the Frankfurt Cohort, for example, higher viral load was not associated with disease progression

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or death among patients taking protease inhibitors who achieved good CD₄ cell increases.

Conversely, other people on HAART experience good virological suppression without a substantial increase in CD₄ cells. This tends to occur more often among people with advanced immune suppression and highly treatment-experienced people with extensive drug resistance.

A retrospective review of more than 1000 patients at Chelsea and Westminster Hospital in London found that after one year on HAART, 16% did not achieve CD₄ cell increases of more than 50 cells/mm³ despite viral load suppression, although about half of these did so after a further year of treatment. Among more than 1200 individuals in the UK Collaborative HIV Cohort (CHIC) who achieved an undetectable viral load four to eight months after starting HAART, 41% did not experience at least a 100 cells/mm³ rise during this period, but the proportion gradually fell with more time on therapy.

Minimal CD₄ cell increases might not be a problem for patients who start treatment early, when their CD₄ cell counts are still close to normal levels and do not have much room for improvement. But persistently low CD₄ cell counts are associated with HIV disease progression and death, even in people with viral load suppression [1].

A recent Canadian study of 300 treatment-naive patients starting therapy with a median CD₄ cell count of 80 cells/mm³, for example, found that about one-third failed to attain CD₄ counts of 200 cells/mm³ or higher after one year, despite viral load suppression. These individuals were more likely to experience disease progression, having a 10% risk of AIDS-related clinical events.

In summary, while viral load below 50 copies/ml may be optimal for avoiding disease progression, patients can still derive substantial immune recovery with a lesser degree of viral suppression, at least in the short term. This is an important consideration for highly treatment-experienced patients, who may be unable to achieve an undetectable viral load using current anti-HIV drugs. Discordant immunological and virological responses may not persist over the long term, however, as CD₄ cell counts tend to eventually rise in people with viral load suppression and fall in those with ongoing HIV replication.

Viral load-general observations

The CD₄ cell count and HIV viral load (RNA level) are closely linked to HIV-related illness and mortality. They give prognostic information on HIV progression and on response to therapy.

The HIV-1 viral load measurement indicates the number of copies of HIV-1 RNA per milliliter of plasma. Although HIV ultimately resides within cells, the plasma measurement is an accurate reflection of the burden of infection and the magnitude of viral replication. It is used to assess the risk of disease progression and can help guide initiation of therapy. It is critical in monitoring virologic response to ART.

There are several commercially available HIV-1 viral load assays and numerous institution-specific assays. The range of detectable virus differs somewhat with each test, but the lowest level of detection generally is 20-75 copies/ml. A viral load below this “undetectable” level indicates the inability of the assay to detect HIV in the plasma, but does not indicate absence or clearance of the virus from the body. The highest levels of detection of the viral load assays typically are between 500,000 copies/ml and 750,000 copies/ml. Viral loads higher than these levels are reported, for example, as >500,000 copies/ml. Note that commercially available assays may not detect HIV-2, and they do not accurately quantify it [2].

After initial infection with HIV, the viral load quickly peaks to very high levels, usually >100,000 copies/ml. During the period of acute infection, when HIV antibody testing may indicate negative results, the viral load test may be used to detect HIV infection. Generally, 3-6 months after primary infection, the viral load declines and then levels off, remaining in a steady state. Among patients who are not taking ARV medications, a small number maintain a low or even undetectable viral load, but the vast majority of those patients have relatively high HIV RNA levels.

Viral loads, like CD₄ counts, are affected by laboratory variation, assay fluctuations, and patient variables such as acute illness and recent vaccinations. Variations of <0.5 log₁₀ copies/ml (threefold) usually are not clinically significant. Viral load results that are inconsistent with previous trends should be repeated, and treatment decisions usually

should be based on two or more similar values. Recent illnesses or vaccinations can transiently increase viral load. If a patient has had a recent illness or vaccination, the viral load measurement should be deferred for 4 weeks, if possible.

Persistently low CD₄ counts in patients with suppressed HIV RNA

Among patients who take antiretroviral therapy and achieve suppression of HIV RNA levels, most have a substantial increase in their CD₄ cell count [2]. Typically, patients have a brisk increase in CD₄ cells in the first 3 to 6 months after starting antiretroviral therapy, predominantly due to a release of memory CD₄ cells trapped within the lymphoid tissue. In the second phase of CD₄ recovery, there is a gradual increase in CD₄ counts that continues for 3 to 6 years; this phase involves both naive CD₄ cells (from the thymus) and memory CD₄ cells. Approximately one-third of patients who maintain continuous suppression of HIV do not recover their CD₄ cell count to a level above 500 cells/mm³ after 5 years. A smaller proportion of patients (less than 10%) fail to recover their CD₄ count at a level greater than 200 cells/mm³ despite virologic suppression. This is often referred to as a “discordant” or “immuno-virological discordant” response (good virologic response and poor immunologic recovery). This discordant response is associated with increased risk for developing an opportunistic infection and increased progression to AIDS or death [3, 4, 5, 6] but the risk of developing new AIDS-defining event declines substantially after the first 6 months of virologic suppression. “Discordant responses” can also refer to good immunologic responses despite incomplete virologic suppression, but the following discussion will address only discordant responses with poor immunologic recovery.

Immunologic recovery based on specific antiretroviral regimens

Most patients who achieve sustained virologic suppression with one of the recommended modern antiretroviral therapy regimens have good CD₄ count recovery. Existing data suggest that in antiretroviral-naïve patients, efavirenz (*Sustiva*) produces lower CD₄ cell count recovery than with boosted-protease inhibitors [7] maraviroc (*Selzentry*) [8] and raltegravir

(*Isentress*) [9]. In AIDS, Clinical Trial Group (ACTG 5142), patients receiving lopinavir-ritonavir (*Kaletra*) plus two nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs) had greater CD₄ cell count increases at 96 weeks than patients taking efavirenz plus two NRTIs (287 versus 230 cells/mm³). A meta-analysis reported that mean CD₄ cell count increases at week 48 were better with a ritonavir-boosted protease inhibitor regimen (+200 cells/mm³) than a non-boosted protease inhibitor regimen (+179 cells/mm³) or a nonnucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NNRTI)-based regimen (+173 cells/mm³) [10]. This meta-analysis, however, had multiple confounding factors, and the NNRTI-based regimens included data for nevirapine. Analysis of the Swiss National Institute of Health Cohort study also showed a trend for better CD₄ responses with boosted-protease inhibitor regimens [11]. Similar CD₄ cell count recovery occurs with most, but not all, NRTIs. The combination of tenofovir (*Viread*) and didanosine (*Videx*) has been associated with lower CD₄ cell count responses, particularly when the didanosine dose exceeds 4.1 mg/kg [12]. In addition, zidovudine-based regimens may have poorer CD₄ count responses, presumably because of the marrow suppressive effect of zidovudine [13].

Causes of discordant responses with poor immunologic recovery

When patients have poor CD₄ cell count responses in the setting of sustained virologic suppression, several potential reversible causes should be considered, including receipt of marrow suppressive medications and infiltrative bone marrow processes. Common marrow suppressive drugs used in HIV-infected patients include zidovudine (*Retrovir*) and zidovudine containing fixed combination pills (*Combivir* and *Trizivir*), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (*Bactrim*, *Septra*), interferon and peginterferon (*Pegasys* or *PegIntron*), pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine, ganciclovir (*Cytovene*), valganciclovir (*Valcyte*), and etoposide. Medication-related marrow suppression is more likely to occur when a combination of marrow suppressive agents such as zidovudine plus trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole are used. Marrow infiltrative processes, such as lymphoma and disseminated histoplasmosis, should also be considered. Only after excluding reversible causes of poor immunologic response should the

patient be considered to have a true discordant response with poor immunologic recovery. Factors identified with poor immunologic recovery include low baseline CD₄ cell count [14, 15, 16], older age, and possibly co-infection with hepatitis C virus [17].

Interleukin-2 for persistently low CD₄ cell counts

Several studies clearly established that interleukin-2 (*Aldesleukin*) given with antiretroviral therapy causes substantially greater increases in CD₄ cell counts than antiretroviral therapy alone [18]. In contrast, interleukin-2 given without antiretroviral therapy generates inferior CD₄ count responses when compared with antiretroviral therapy alone [19]. These studies, however, did not evaluate the clinical impact of interleukin-2 therapy. Patients who have a discordant response and CD₄ counts persistently less than 200 cells/mm³ were of interest for potential investigational use of interleukin-2. Specifically, the hope was that patients with sustained virologic suppression but poor immunologic recovery could substantially increase their CD₄ cell count using interleukin-2, thereby reducing their risk of opportunistic infection and death. To determine whether the addition of interleukin-2 to antiretroviral therapy reduced the risk of opportunistic diseases or death, the NIH sponsored two large phase 3, randomized, international trials: (1) Evaluation of Subcutaneous Proleukin in a Randomized International Trial (ESPRIT) and (2) Subcutaneous Recombinant Human IL-2 in HIV-infected Patients with Low CD₄ Counts under Active Antiretroviral Therapy (SILCAAT) [20]. In ESPRIT, 4,111 patients with CD₄ counts greater than 350 cells/mm³ were randomized to receive interleukin-2 (7.5 MIU twice daily for 5 consecutive days every 8 weeks for at least 6 months) plus antiretroviral therapy or antiretroviral therapy alone; patients had an average follow-up of 7 years [20]. Although patients who received interleukin-2 and antiretroviral therapy had an average increase in CD₄ count that was 159 cells/mm³ greater than the group receiving antiretroviral therapy alone, there were no differences in clinical outcomes. Investigators in SILCAAT randomized 1,695 patients with a CD₄ cell count between 50 and 299 cells/mm³ to receive interleukin-2 plus antiretroviral therapy or antiretroviral therapy alone, with follow-up of approximately 7 years. Interleukin-2 was

given at a dose of 4.5 MIU twice daily for 5 consecutive days every 8 weeks for 49 weeks. Patients who received interleukin-2 and antiretroviral therapy had an average CD₄ count 53 cells/mm³ greater than those who received antiretroviral therapy alone, but no differences in clinical outcomes were observed. The reason for the lack of clinical benefit despite increased CD₄ counts remains unclear.

Recommendations for patients with persistently low CD₄ cell counts

For people who have sustained virologic suppression for at least 2 years but have CD₄ counts consistently less than 200 cells/mm³, the following approach is recommended. First, make certain the patient is receiving appropriate prophylaxis for opportunistic infections. Second, examine the patient's medication list for medications that can suppress bone marrow. In patients taking a potentially marrow suppressive drug, change the medication to a non-marrow suppressive drug, if possible. For example, consider switching from a zidovudine-containing regimen to a regimen that does not contain zidovudine. Third, evaluate the patient for clinical manifestations, such as systemic symptoms or pancytopenia, which suggest a marrow infiltrative process. Fourth, continue antiretroviral therapy, even if the patient has not had a good CD₄ cell count response. Multiple studies have shown that achieving a durable virologic response translates into clinical benefit independent of CD₄ count [21]. There are no "switch" data that support a change from one suppressive regimen to another, although the combination of tenofovir plus didanosine (especially at full dose) should be avoided, and there may be potential benefit of switching to a non-zidovudine-containing regimen. There is evidence, discussed above, that regimens containing ritonavir-boosted protease inhibitors, maraviroc, and raltegravir result in greater CD₄ cell count responses than efavirenz-based regimens, although there is currently little evidence supporting modification or intensification of efavirenz-based regimens in patients with discordant CD₄ responses. The intensification approach is currently being evaluated in clinical trials. Finally, existing data do not support the use of interleukin-2 in this setting. Although preliminary data with other investigational agents, such as

interleukin-7, have demonstrated an increase in CD₄ cell counts, there are no clinical data to support the use of such therapies in clinical practice [22].

Conclusion

HIV-positive patients on HAART may show discordance in the CD₄ and viral load counts. Immunological and virological responses can be an important factor in determining the survival rate of the patients. This should be kept in mind by clinicians while monitoring the progression of HIV disease. Little is known about the pathogenesis of discordant responses, which seems to depend on the interaction of a multitude of viral, host and treatment-related factors. Further research is required to understand the risk factors and pathogenesis, prognosis and clinical management associated with the discordant treatment responses despite its relative frequency. There is a need to develop a standardized and universally accepted definition for discordant response which will help in defining the therapy responses having clinical significance for the patients and designing trials of possible therapeutic interventions.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

This paper does not have any conflict of interests

REFERENCES

1. Battegay, M., Nüesch, R., Hirschel, B. and Kaufmann, G. R. 2006, *Lancet Infect. Dis.*, 6, 280-7.
2. Centers for Disease Control. 1993 revised classification system for HIV infection and expanded surveillance case definition for AIDS among adolescents and adults. 1992, *MMWR Recomm. Rep.*, 41(RR-17), 1-19
3. Cesarman, E., Chang, Y., Moore, P. S., Said, J. W. and Knowles, D. M. 1995, *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 332, 1186-91.
4. Sullivan, R. J., Pantanowitz, L., Casper, C., Stebbing, J. and Dezube, B. J. 2008, *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, 47, 1209-15.
5. Mellors, J. W., Rinaldo, C. R. Jr., Gupta, P., White, R. M., Todd, J. A. and Kingsley, L. A. 1996, *Science*, 272, 1167-70.
6. Maartens, M., Celum, C. and Sharon, R. L. 2014, 384, 258-271.
7. Zidovudine, didanosine, and zalcitabine in the treatment of HIV infection: meta-analyses of the randomised evidence. HIV Trialists' Collaborative Group. 1999, *Lancet*, 353, 2014-25.
8. Sterling, T. R., Chaisson, R. E., Keruly, J. and Moore, R. D. 2003, *J. Infect. Dis.*, 188, 1659-65.
9. Sterling, T. R., Chaisson, R. E. and Moore, R. D. 2003, *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, 36, 812-5.
10. Hughes, M. D. and Ribaud, H. R. 2008, *J. Infect. Dis.*, 197, 1084-1086.
11. Stevenson, M. 2003, *Nat. Med.*, 9, 853-60.
12. Greene, W. C. and Peterlin, B. M. 2002, *Nat. Med.*, 8, 673-80.
13. Wilen, C. B., Tilton, J. C. and Doms, R.W. 2012, *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.*, 726, 223-42.
14. Haqqani, A. A. and Tilton, J. C. 2013, *Antiviral Res.*, 98, 158-70.
15. Wilkin, T. J. and Gulick, R. M. 2012, *Annu. Rev. Med.*, 63, 81-93.
16. Pommier, Y., Johnson, A. A. and Marchand, C. 2005, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.*, 4, 236-48.
17. Flexner, C. 1998. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 338, 1281-92.
18. Molina, J. M., Clumeck, N., Redant, K., Rimsky, L., Vanveggel, S. and Stevens, M. 2013, *AIDS*, 27, 889-97.
19. Molina, J. M., Clumeck, N., Orkin, C., Rimsky, L. T., Vanveggel, S. and Stevens, M. 2013, *HIV Med.*, 15, 57-62.
20. Gandhi, R. T. 2007, *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, 44, 438-40.
21. World Health Organization. Scaling up antiretroviral therapy in resource-limited settings. Guidelines for a public health approach. Executive Summary April 2002, Geneva, Switzerland.
22. Umeh, O. C. and Currier, J. S. 2005, *Curr. Infect. Dis. Rep.*, 7, 73-8.